

pulmonary lesions treated by hepatic metastasectomy and chemotherapy. Two residual pulmonary lesions demonstrated by PET were planned to be treated by radiotherapy. The actual home therapy of the patient was pantoprazole 20mg/die, prednisone 25mg/die, Vit-D 2500IU/die, propranolol 40mg/die, triazolam 0,25mg/die. ECG done at admission was normal. Blood examinations done at h12:05 showed neutrophilia and no other worrying results (table 1). At h 13:42 an head, cervical and total body CT scan plus detailed left arm X-ray was performed with study for bone and parenchyma: there were fractures of the IX,X,XI and XII left ribs but no other major consequences of trauma, nor major brain and truncal parenchymal damages apart the sequelae of the known oncologic disease. The neuroradiologist just signalled: *“at sovratentorial level slight hypo-density of the white periventricular substance”*. At h 14:50 the neurological status of the patient deteriorated to GCS11 (E3, V3, M5) with recurrent tonic contraction of both arms. After wound revision, tetanus immunoglobulin, antibiotic coverage, fentanyl 0,1 mg im and more diazepam 5 mg iv he was admitted to the emergency sub-intensive ward with prescription for leviracetam 500 mg iv bid and diagnosis of *“epilepsy with recurrent tonic crisis in no concussion head trauma by accidental fall; fracture of the left ribs IX,X,XI,XII; one nodulation on the upper lobe of the right lung in oncologic sequelae of operated rectal cancer on follow-up”*. During afternoon the level of consciousness of the patient deteriorated further and at 23:25 the GCS was 4 (E2 V1 M1) with dolls’ eyes phenomenon, normal vitals and no fever. No more tonic crisis was observed. Blood examinations done at h20:00 (table 1) demonstrated a reducing haemoglobin and fibrinogen with increasing CPR and lymphopenia with high N/L ratio. In presence of visibly increasing subcutaneous haematomas at cranial level and on the left chest an E-FAST done at bed was negative for significant internal bleeding. A control brain CT was done at 01:13 confirming no relevant cerebral trauma damages and same level of slight hypo-density of the white substance as already observed. An EEG done at h03:21 showed diffuse slowing with Delta frequency band without clear irritative signs. A first pharyngeal swab for SARS-CoV2 search (Seegene Allplex^(TM) 2019 nCoV Assay) was negative (table 2). In the morning of day 14 the patient was still comatose; temperature was 37.3°C with tachypnoea at RR 26/min and respiratory condition was rapidly deteriorating requiring Oxygen therapy at high flux. A MRI-DWI was performed demonstrating *“multiple extensive clear micro-spots of restricted diffusion at level pontinum, hemispheric left cerebellum, right posterior cerebellum, sovra-tentorial bi-hemispheric cortico-subcorticalis, symmetrical medium talamis and left lenticularis, of probable micro-embolic or micro-angiopathic nature”*. The brain angio-CT performed shortly after did not demonstrate significant stenosis of the cranial vessels. The blood examinations done at h08:00 and 20:00 demonstrated a further decrease in haemoglobin and lymphocyte count with signals of a rampaging inflammatory response by high CRP and ferritin, and very high D-dimer level (table 1). NG tube in place and central venous access obtained, a diagnosis of suspect neuro-COVID-19 was formulated and therapy started with hydroxychloroquine 400mg qd, azithromycin 500 mg qd., methylprednisolone 40mg iv bid, enoxaparin sc 100 IU/kg bid, plus antibiotic coverage, enteral NG feeding and fluid balance maintained. A second pharyngeal swab done on day 15 was positive for SARS-CoV2 (table 2). Anti-SARS-CoV2 IgG and IgM remained negative. Lumbar puncture was done in the afternoon of day 16 showing proteinorrachia in crystal clear CSF as for blood-brain barrier disruption. RT-PCR demonstrated the presence of nonspecific Coronavirus antigen-E in the CSF (table 2). At this time the patient was already on Oxygen mask with reservoir FiO₂ 1.0, enough to maintain SpO₂ >90% and acceptable PaO₂ levels. A second chest and abdomen CT scan was performed on day April 17 (figure 2) demonstrating the presence of bi-basal pleural fluid (max thickness 20mm) and multiple bilateral areas of “crazy paving” thickening. In the following days, despite some slight improvement of the EEG rhythm showing diffuse theta rhythm with no reaction to pain and mitigation of the blood inflammatory indexes (table1) the patient neurological examination was still extremely severe with GCS 3. After meeting with intensivists and neurologists a joint decision was taken in consideration of the clinical picture, expected outcome, comorbidities, age of the patient and general situation, not to proceed to more aggressive ventilation support. The patient was transferred to the neurologic ward where a second lumbar puncture confirmed the suspicion for a viral encephalitic type liquor pattern (table 3). CSF analysis for the detection of other neurotropic viral antigens gave no result, as well as the research for paraneoplastic autoantibodies. A search for serum oncologic markers gave no

results. SARS-CoV2 / Coronavirus antigens were not found any more in CSF at this time. The immunoblot analysis showed the presence of IgG on both CSF and plasma, with an increase in CSF/plasma ratio for albumin and IgG, as usual in blood-brain barrier disruption. Interestingly, flow cytometry immunophenotyping excluded leptomeningeal carcinomatosis, and revealed a prevalence of CD14⁺ monocytes and macrophages (75% of WBC population). On the other hand, T cells accounted for only 25% of the whole WBC population, with an inversion of CD4⁺/CD8⁺ ratio.

In the absence of any improvement of the consciousness state and in face of worsening cardiorespiratory function the patient died on the morning of day April 26. Due to technical constraint related to general situation autopsy was not feasible.

A final diagnosis of COVID-19 with neurologic presentation was formulated. Case reports of central nervous system involvement in COVID-19 are now increasingly reported^{1,2}. In our case the strict chronological link between an accidental trauma and the onset of symptoms may be presumptive of some pathogenetic role of the trauma itself, though we cannot exclude that epileptic crisis secondary to brain damage came first.

Laboratory data at the arrival in ED, especially neutrophilia with lymphopenia, correlated with the CD4⁺/CD8⁺ inversion in CSF, and supported the diagnosis of COVID-19 infection, characterised by massive mononuclear cell infiltration in several tissues³. An expansion of CD14⁺ CD16⁺ monocytes producing IL6 has been described in serum of severe SARS COV2 patients⁴ highlighting the role of mononuclear cells in enhancing the inflammatory response. In addition to that, monocytes are also responsible for activating the coagulation pathway leading to hypercoagulation and microvascular damage⁵ as seen in the brain MRI of our patient.

Moreover, the presence of Coronavirus in CSF is not established. Some authors reported negative findings in CSF of patients with neurological symptoms and a positive nasal swab⁶ while recently Moriguchi and coll. described a patient whom nasopharyngeal swab was negative but the specific Coronavirus 19 RNA was detected in CSF⁷ We believe this report add to the knowledge about the presence of a Coronavirus in CSF.

Of course, we cannot answer to the “causality or casualty” question. However, this report can be instrumental to identify this possible link in case other clinicians will observe similar conditions.

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Tab.1: laboratory results

Tab 1	Laboratory	13/04/2020	13/04/2020	14/04/2020	14/04/2020	16/04/2020	23/04/2020
item	nv	h12:05	h20:00	h08:00	h20:00	h07:00	h07:00
RBC	4.5-6.3 x 10 ⁶ /μl	4,79	3,75	3,35	2,84	2,57	2,94
Hb	g/dl	14,5	11,3	10,2	8,5	7,8	8,6
PLT	140-440 x 10 ³ /μl	171	134	96	68	55	157
Neut	1.52-7.4 x 10 ³ /μl	14,22	19,09	13,75	10,74	6,86	15,24
Lymph	0.76-4.5 x 10 ³ /μl	0,87	0,35	0,74	0,21	0,16	0,43
N/L ratio		16,3	54,5	18,6	51,1	42,9	35,4
aPTT ratio	0.83-1.27	1,56	1,27	1,2	na	1,2	0,96
Fibrinog	200-400 mg/dl	165	79	229	na	565	457
D-dimer	<500 μg/l	na	na	na	60768	4770	6980
LDH	120-248 U/l	na	600	456	440	383	552
CPK	<171 U/l	135	180	290	229	117	47
Ferritin	23.9-336.2 μg/l	na	na	na	661	465	419
CRP	0-5 mg/l	1,5	24,8	170,3	258,7	246	132,6
Procalcitonin	<0.05 ng/ml	na	na	na	na	0,88	na
L-Troponin I HS	ng/l	na	na	na	na	134,8	na
Aptoglobin	0.3-2 g/l	na	na	na	0,96	na	na
NH3	16-53 μmol/l	67	na	na	na	na	na
Na ⁺	136-145 mmol/l	139	138	140	140	151	140
K ⁺	3.5-5 mmol/l	na	4,6	5,2	4,4	3,8	3,6
Glucose	74-106 mg/dl	121	124	111	151	148	130
Creatinine	0.67-1.17 mg/dl	0,76	0,82	1,41	1,36	0,73	0,36
GOT	1-50 UI	na	43	40	43	30	45
GPT	1-50 UI	50	45	39	34	22	51
Bil direct	0.1-0.3 mg/dl	na	0,44	0,29	0,49	0,42	na
Bil indirect	0.1-0.9 mg/dl	na	1,73	1,64	1,46	1,13	na

Tab 2: RT-PCR for SARS-CoV2

Tab2: RT-PCR for SARS-Cov2. Seegene Allplex™ 2019-nCoV Assay .					
	Date	14/04/2020	15/04/2020	16/04/2020	23/04/2020
Analytes	Specificity	pharyngeal swab	pharyngeal swab	liquor	tracheal aspirate
RdRP gene	SARS-CoV2	-	+	-	-
N gene	SARS-CoV2	-	+	-	-
E gene	All Sarbecovirus	-	-	+	-

Fig 1: brain DWI and FLAIR images 04/14/2020

a) DWI assial

b) FLAIR assial

c) DWI talamus

d) FLAIR talamus

Fig 2: CT chest image 04/17/2020

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